

ment of the compounds was based on their elemental analyses and ir and pmr spectral data.

The ir spectra for all the compounds **3** revealed identical bands at 3 500–3 350 (OH), 1 640–1 620 (C=O conjugated) and 1 600–1 490 cm^{-1} (phenyl). The pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of **3a**, showed signals at δ 2.20 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.60 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.8–5.6 (1H, s, OH) and 6.9–8 (8H, m, ArH). The ir spectra for the compounds **4** revealed identical bands at 3 450–3 300 (OH), 1 690–1 640 (C=N, pyrimidine). In the pmr spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of **4a**, signals have been observed at δ 2.56 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.8–5.2 (1H, s, OH) and 7.13–8.10 (8H, m, ArH).

Antibacterial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity using cup-plate method⁴ at a concentration of 5 mg ml^{-1} against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Compounds **4h**, **4l** and **4p** were found inactive against both the organisms. Other compounds showed a moderate or weak activity against *S. aureus*. Compounds **4a** and **4k** showed a very strong inhibition and others showed a medium activity against *E. coli*.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4*

Compd no	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	M p °C	Yield %
4a	H	OCH_3	H	H	101	60
b	H	OCH_3	NO_2	H	135	70
c	H	OCH_3	Br	H	140	65
d	Br	OCH_3	NO_2	H	155	72
e	H	OC_2H_5	H	H	125	62
f	H	OC_2H_5	NO_2	H	168	73
g	H	OC_2H_5	Br	H	116	68
h	Br	OC_2H_5	NO_2	H	138	70
i	H	OCH_3	H	OCH_3	110	60
j	H	OCH_3	NO_2	OCH_3	175	75
k	H	OCH_3	B ₁	OCH_3	160	70
l	B ₁	OCH_3	NO_2	OCH_3	158	72
m	H	OC_2H_5	H	OCH_3	90	55
n	H	OC_2H_5	NO_2	OCH_3	180	72
o	H	OC_2H_5	Br	OCH_3	152	66
p	Br	OC_2H_5	NO_2	OCH_3	170	80

*All compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (100 MHz) on a XL-100A spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

o-Aroyloxyacetophenone (2a–h): 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (**1**; 0.1 mol), dissolved in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (75 ml) was treated with redistilled benzoyl chloride (0.1 mol) and the mixture shaken vigorously for 15–20 min. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

o-Aroyloxyacetophenone (2i–p): 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (**1**; 0.1 mol) and anisic acid (0.11 mol) were dissolved in dry pyridine (60 ml). The solution

was kept in a cold water-bath and phosphorous oxychloride (0.07 mol) was added to it dropwise with constant stirring maintaining the temperature below 50°. After 3 h the mixture was decomposed by cold dilute HCl (1 : 1). The resulting solid was washed with water and 10% sodium bicarbonate solution, and recrystallised from 95% ethanol. Their alcoholic solutions did not give colour with FeCl_3 solution.

2'-Hydroxydibenzoylmethane (3a–p): A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol), dry pyridine (25 ml) and powdered KOH (0.05 mol) was stirred for about 30 min and allowed to stand for 0.5 h. The reaction mixture on acidification with dilute HCl gave a yellow solid which was washed with 10% bicarbonate solution followed by water and recrystallised from ethanol. It gave deep violet colouration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

2-Hydroxy-4-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (4a–p): A mixture of **3** (0.01 mol) and urea (0.01 mol) in ethylene glycol (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h and then poured into cold water with stirring. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (Table I).

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Reaction of Ethylchloroformate with 1-Alkyl/ Aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets in Presence of Ketones

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of new s-triazine derivatives as potential antimicrobial agents¹, we now report an interesting reaction of ethyl chloroformate with dithiobiurets (**1**) in the

presence of ketones, leading to the formation of 'true' keturet² derivatives.

1-Methyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (1; R=Me) and ethyl chloroformate in acetone, on standing for 10–20 minutes, afforded colourless crystalline compound (3; Scheme 1). Compound 3 was acidic and when dissolved in water readily decomposed to afford the methyl dithiobiuret (1) and acetone. On treatment with warm aqueous alkali followed by acidification, it gave 1,6,6-trimethyl-2,4-dithio-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (4), which on benzylation gave the corresponding 4-S-alkyl derivative (5).

Compound 3 can be directly synthesised by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas through a solution of 1 and the corresponding ketones.

The filtrate after removing 3 (R=Me) afforded 3-carbethoxy-1-methyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (6). Further identification was done by its oxidation with bromine to 5-methylimino-3-carbethoxy-2-imino-1,2,4-dithi-

azolidine hydrobromide (7). The latter on reaction with aniline gave 5-phenylamino-3-carbethoxy-1-methylthiocarbamide (8).

Earlier workers² proposed the structure 4 (1,3,5-triazine) for the keturets. It can now be seen that 'true' keturets are the alkylidene dithiobiurets (3) which could then be converted into 4.

Experimental

1-Alkyl/aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets were prepared by the reported method³ by the action of aryl/alkyl-amine on isoperthiocyanic acid.

5-Alkylidene/arylidene-1-alkyl/aryl-2,4-dithiobiuret (3): Methyl dithiobiuret (1; R=Me, 3 g) in dry acetone (10 ml) and ethyl chloroformate (3 ml) were mixed together when an exothermic reaction set in. After keeping the mixture overnight, the resulting solid (2.5 g) was washed with little acetone

NOTES

and purified by dissolving it in absolute alcohol followed by reprecipitation with dry ether, m.p. 168°, m/z 225 (M^+) (Found: C, 32.3; H, 5.2; N, 18.4; S, 27.9. $C_6H_{11}N_3S_2HCl$ required: C, 31.9; H, 4.9; N, 18.3; S, 28.3%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 440 sh, 3 120, 1 630s (C=N), 1 550, 1 510, 1 300, 1 210, 1 110, 1 068 and 820 cm^{-1} ; m/z 225 (M^+) and 189 ($M-HCl$)⁺. It was desulphurised when treated with alkali plumbite solution. On treatment with warm water it gave acetone and methyl dithiobiuret (m.p., m.m.p. 153° with authentic sample); the latter was confirmed by Feigl's test⁴. The reaction product was thus identified as 5-isopropylidene-1-methyl-2,4-dithiobiuret hydrochloride (3). Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

Examination of the filtrate from reaction of 1 with ethyl chloroformate in acetone: The filtrate obtained from the reaction of ethyl chloroformate with 1 in acetone was evaporated at room temperature and the residue treated with cold concentrated HCl, when shining needles were obtained (1 g) which were crystallised from water, m.p. 110° (Found: C, 32.0; H, 5.1; N, 19.1; S, 28.5. $C_6H_{11}N_3S_2O_2$ requires: C, 32.12; H, 4.97; N, 19.0; S, 28.95%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300, 3 160 (NH) and 1 705 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ (DMSO- d_6) 8.8 (1H, s, NH), 9.7 (2H, s, NH₂), 3.8 (2H, q, COOCH₂), 3.3 (3H, s, NCH₃) and 1.34 (3H, t, CH₃). Pyrolysis afforded thiocyanic acid as the main product. The compound was identified as 3-carbethoxy-1-methyl dithiobiuret⁶.

Ethyl dithiobiuret (1; R=Et) likewise gave 3-carbethoxy-1-ethyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (6; R=Et), m.p. 141°, on treatment with ethyl chloroformate in acetone.

Oxidation of 6 to 7: Compound 6 (R=Me; 1 g) in chloroform was treated with excess of bromine and the resulting solid was reprecipitated from its alcoholic solution with dry ether (1 g), m.p. 220°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 221 (NH), 1 711 (C=O) and 1 620 cm^{-1} (C=N). On treatment with alkali, elemental sulphur was obtained. The product was identified as 5-methylimino-3-carbethoxy-2-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine hydrobromide (7 R=Me), which on heating with aniline in alcohol afforded 3-phenylamidino-3-carbethoxy-1-methylthiocarbamide (8), m.p. 260°.

Formation of 1,6,6-trimethyl-2,4-dithio-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (4) from (3): Compound 3 (3 g) was warmed with aqueous NaOH (15 ml) and then cooled in ice. On treatment with dilute HCl, a solid (2.2 g) was obtained, which was washed with water and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 230° (Found: C, 37.7; H, 5.1; N, 22.1; S, 33.66. $C_6H_{11}N_3S_2$ requires: C, 37.5; H, 5.0; N, 22.22; S, 33.86%), M^+ m/z 189; ν_{max} 3 160 (NH), 1 245, 1 160 and 1 122 cm^{-1} (C=S); δ (DMSO- d_6) 10.2 (1H, s, CS-NH-CS-), 9.75 (1H, s, C-NH-CS-), 2.32 (3H, s, NCH₃) and 1.55 (6H, s, CH₃-C-CH₃). It was identified as 1,6,6-trimethyl-2,4-dithio-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (4).

Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PREPARATION AND M.P. DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Sl. no.	Dithiobiuret (1) R (amount, g)	Ketone used 2 R ₁ /R ₂	5-Alkylidene derivative 3 (Mol. formula)	Ketone HCl(1) M.p. (°C)/ (Yield)	s-Triazine (4)	M.p. °C
1.	Me (3)	Acetone R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Et R ₁ =Me R ₂ =isobu	R ₁ =R ₂ =Me R=Me (C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	168 (2.1)	R=Me; R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Me	230
			R=R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Et (C ₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	162 (1.68)	R ₂ =Et R=R ₁ =Me	187
			R=R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Isobu (C ₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	184 (1.8)	R=CH ₃ ; R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	215
			R=Et, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Me (C ₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	167 (2.4)	R=Et; R ₁ =Me=R ₂ R=Et, R ₁ =Me	207
2.	Et (3)	R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ R ₁ =CH ₃ R ₂ =Et R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	R=Et, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Me (C ₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	172 (1.8)	R ₂ =Et R=Et, R ₁ =Me	228
			R=Et, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Isobu (C ₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	182 (2.3)	R=Et, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	246
			R=Ph, R ₁ =R ₂ =Me (C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	195 (2.0)	R=Ph, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Me	230
			R=Ph, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Et (C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	147 (2.5)	R=Ph, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Et	204
3.	Ph (3)	Acetone R ₁ =R ₂ =Me R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Et R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	R=Ph, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Isobu (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	195 (2.2)	R=Ph, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	228
			R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =R ₂ =Me (C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	212 (2.0)	R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R=R=Me	255
			R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Et (C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	198 (1.8)	R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Et	219
			R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =isobu (C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	203 (1.8)	R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me R=Isobu	225
4.	<i>p</i> -Tol (3)	Acetone R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Et R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	R=Ph, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Isobu (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	195 (2.2)	R=Ph, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Isobu	228
			R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =R ₂ =Me (C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	212 (2.0)	R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R=R=Me	255
			R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =Et (C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	198 (1.8)	R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me R ₂ =Et	219
			R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me, R ₂ =isobu (C ₁₅ H ₂₁ N ₃ S ₂ .HCl)	203 (1.8)	R= <i>p</i> -Tol, R ₁ =Me R=Isobu	225

Methylation of 4: A mixture of **4** ($R_1=R_2=R_3=Me$; 1.5 g), methyl iodide (0.8 ml) and absolute alcohol (5 ml) were refluxed for 1.5 h. On cooling, the isolated solid was reprecipitated with dry ether (1 g), m.p. 205° (Found: N, 12.61; S, 19.24. $C_7H_{13}N_3S_2 \cdot HI$ requires: N, 12.71; S, 19.33%). It was identified as 1,6,6-trimethyl-4-methylmercapto-2-thio-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine hydriodide (**5**, $R_4=Me$).

Benzylation of 4: A mixture of **4** ($R_1=R_2=R_3=Me$), benzyl chloride and sodium hydroxide in molar proportions in alcohol under similar reaction conditions as described above gave **5** ($R_4=benzyl$), m.p. 116°.

5-Alkylidene-1-aryl/alkyl-2,4-dithiobiuret hydrochloride (3): Methyl dithiobiuret (**1**, $R=Me$; 3 g) was dissolved in acetone (30 ml) and the solution cooled in ice. Through the cooled solution was passed a dry stream of hydrogen chloride when **3** (4.2 g) was obtained, m.p. 169°. It showed no depression in m.p. with the product obtained by the reaction of ethyl chloroformate with methyl dithiobiuret. Its spectrum (KBr) showed perfect superimposability. The other products obtained are given in Table I. Compounds **3** obtained by the above procedure were converted into **4** by alkali as described earlier, which also showed no depression in m.m.p and the ir spectra being superimposable.

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Synthesis and Biological Activity of 2-Phthalimidomethyl-3-(3-substituted-aminomethyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-substituted/6,8-disubstituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-quinazolines

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SEVERAL 2,3-disubstituted-4-quinazolines¹ and methaqualone, 2-methyl-2-(*o*-tolyl)-3H-4-quinazolinone have been reported to possess CNS activities. Aminomethyl pharmacophores in many compounds^{3,4} yielded the pharmacologically active compounds while profound anticonvulsant activity was observed in morpholines⁵ and piperidines⁶. It was therefore considered of interest to synthesise some newer quinazolinones (Scheme 1) and screen them for their CNS activity.

Compounds **4e-h** were prepared by condensing **3a-d** with 4-aminophenol. **3a-d** intermediates were obtained by reacting substituted-anthranilic acids with phthalimidocetyl chloride in dry pyridine at 0–5°. Compounds **5i-w** were obtained by Mannich reactions of **4e-h** with different secondary amines.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The reactions were followed by tlc. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 157 and 177 or 137 spectrophotometers and pmr spectra ($CDCl_3 + DMSO-d_6$) on a R-32 instrument (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

5-Bromo-⁷, 3,5-dibromo-⁷ and 5-iodoanthranilic acids⁸ and phthalimidoacetic acids⁹ were prepared according to the known methods.

2-Phthalimidomethyl-6-substituted/6,8-disubstituted-4(3H)-oxo-3,1-benzoxazines (3a-d): To a solution of substituted anthranilic acid (0.001 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) at 0°, was added phthalimidocetyl chloride (0.001 mol) slowly in small portions keeping the temperature at 0–5°. It was shaken for 1 h at this temperature and kept overnight at room temperature. Cold dilute hydrochloric acid was then added to it with shaking and the separated crystalline mass was washed with cold water, treated with aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and washed again with cold water, air-dried and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (60%): **a** ($X_1=X_2=H$), m.p. 235–40°; **b** ($X_1=Br$, $X_2=H$), m.p. 110°; **c** ($X_1=X_2=Br$), m.p. 204–05°; **d** ($X_1=I$, $X_2=H$), m.p. 223–28°.